

Sediment Loss Responses to Rainfall on Different Surfaces in Obudu, Cross River State, Nigeria

M. A. Abua^{1*}, P. A. Essoka¹, U. I. Uquetan¹ and S. W. Ashua¹

¹*Department of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria.*

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author MAA designed the study, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author PAE managed the literature searches. Author UIU carried out analyses of the study and author SWA managed the experimental process. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/JGEESI/2017/22200

Editor(s):

- (1) Zeyuan Qiu, Department of Chemistry and Environmental Sciences, New Jersey Institute of Technology, USA.
- (2) Iovine Giulio, CNR-IRPI (National Research Council-Institute of Research for the Geo-hydrologic Protection) of Cosenza, Italy.
- (3) Masum A. Patwary, Geography and Environmental Science, Begum Rokeya University, Bangladesh.

Reviewers:

- (1) Rahul Kumar Jaiswal, National Institute of Hydrology, Bhopal, M.P. India.
 - (2) Edward Ching-Ruey Luo, National Chi-Nan University, Nantou, Taiwan.
 - (3) Jose Navarro-Pedreño, University Miguel Hernández of Elche, Spain.
 - (4) Artemi Cerdà, Universidade Estadual Paulista "Julio de Mesquita Filho", São Paulo, Brazil.
 - (5) Alexandre Marques da Silva, São Paulo State University (UNESP), Ilha Solteira, São Paulo, Brazil.
- Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19901>

Received 22nd September 2015
Accepted 2nd June 2016
Published 6th July 2017

Original Research Article

ABSTRACT

The amount of runoff generated relative to different surface types given an amount of rainfall is very important in hydrogeomorphological studies. This study is aimed at examining sediment yield responses to rainfall on different surfaces in Obudu, Cross River State, Nigeria. Data were collected on rainfall amount, intensity, duration and sediment loss from three run off plots on natural vegetation surface, mulched and bare surfaces. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson's moment correlation and multiple regression statistical techniques. The results revealed that rainfall amount correlated positively with sediment loss on vegetated, mulched and bare surfaces with r-values of 0.58 ($p < 0.01$), 0.57 ($p < 0.01$) and 0.95 ($p < 0.01$) respectively. Rainfall intensity correlated positively with sediment yield on the vegetated, mulched and bare surfaces with r-values of 0.75 ($p < 0.01$), 0.65 ($p < 0.01$) and 0.60 ($p < 0.01$) respectively. The negative correlations between rainfall duration and sediment loss suggests that sediment loss decreases on all the surfaces considered

*Corresponding author: E-mail: ask4mossabua@yahoo.com;

with r-values of - 0.15 ($p < 0.01$), - 0.21 ($P < 0.01$) and -0.06 ($p < 0.01$) on vegetated, mulched and bare surfaces respectively. The study further revealed that the predictive variables explain 62.7%, 50.8 and 60.8% of sediment yield on bared, vegetated and mulched surfaces respectively as rainfall directly influences sediment loss, though the importance of surface types cannot be discarded.

Keywords: Sediment loss; rainfall; surface types and Obudu.

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil loss is a direct consequence of soil erosion which is a function of several environmental factors. These include rainfall amount, intensity and duration, surface configuration (relief/slope); nature of surface materials and vegetation. The nature and magnitude of soil erosion and invariably rate and amount of soil loss (sediment yield) depends on erosivity capacity of rainfall and the nature of surface materials. Erosivity power has to do with the energy involved in breaking down or detaching soil materials, mobilizing and transporting them in overland flow or runoff. The nature of surface materials influences the rate of infiltration, surface runoff as well as stability of soil aggregates and ease with which the soil is detached and entrained [1-5] and [6]. Hence the character of rainfall in terms of intensity, amount and duration, nature of land surface play a vital role in the soil erosion and therefore important in soil loss studies.

Studies have shown that sediment yield or soil loss varies directly as rainfall [5,7] and [8]. Soil erosion takes place first by detachment of soil particles from a catchment area and this is directly proportional to the rainfall intensity in such a catchment [9]. According to [10] the amount of soil loss occurring in an individual storm depends on the supply of loose materials at the surface which could be transported by runoff. In other words, fluvial erosion cannot take place without surface runoff. Though other variables such as soil texture, organic matter content and permeability class determine soil loss, runoff production seems to be the main vehicle that drives and move detached sediments [11]. Thus, without surface runoff, soil will be quite limited.

In addition, runoff also affects sediment yield depending on the nature of vegetation cover and the land surface. The effects of vegetation and mulch covers on rainfall and sediment yield have been examined over the years. The direct effect of vegetation on hydrological processes was investigated by [12], and [13]. Also, the effect of mulching on soil erosion and runoff prediction

has been an area of interest to researchers in recent past e.g. [14,15,16] and [17]. [18] Identified mulch cover as one of the major factors affecting soil loss. In their works [16,17], observed that 90% mulch cover reduced erosion by 93%.

The protective role of vegetation was also examined in the works of [19] where runoff and soil loss were observed to be less significant under cropping than ploughed bare soil. The elimination of surface cover is the greatest cause of erosion. High level of soil erosion was reported after a road construction which disturbed forest cover and floors as sediment yield increased for about 770 times that of undisturbed forest cover [15]. However, the degree and nature of mulch is important here, as it determines its protective ability to a large extent.

Field evaluation has however shown that researches that involve rainfall worked well under natural condition. However, there is the need for an increased knowledge on the relationship between rainfall and sediment loss in the tropics. This study has attempted to create a controlled environment (though natural) where a relatively few, out of the diverse factors that determine the rate of erosion, sediment yield, are examined. The aim of this study therefore is to examine the effects of rainfall along different surfaces on the rate of sediment loss in Obudu environs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Environment

Obudu Local Government Area is located in the northern part of Cross River State, Nigeria. It lies between longitude $8^{\circ}55'$ and $9^{\circ}15'$ east and latitude $6^{\circ}22'$ and $6^{\circ}40'$ north. It is bounded by Benue State in the north, in the south by Boki Local Government Area, in the east and west by Obanliku and Bekwarra Local Government Areas respectively. It is a mountainous area north of the Cross River National Park with an altitude of about 5,000 ft. The area falls within the tropical humid climate. Temperature is fairly high all year

round with pronounced seasonality [20,5] (Fig. 1).

2.2 Field Studies

2.2.1 Rainfall measurement

Rainfall data were gotten from funnel-type rain gauges that were installed on the experimental site and daily rainfall data from the Meteorological Station at Obudu dam. The first ten (10) rain storm events at both the experimental site and at the weather station were correlated.

The contents of the funnel-type rain gauge bottle were poured out into a measuring cylinder to determine the amount of rainfall after each storm.

The difference in the value of the amount and intensity of rainstorms at the two stations were negligible. Consequent upon this, the rainfall data from the Meteorological Station was adopted for the study.

The duration of every rainstorm were recorded and the intensity calculated by dividing the amount of rainfall by the duration.

$$TRI = \frac{RA}{RD} \quad (1)$$

Where TRI is Total Rainfall Intensity

RA is Total Rainfall Amount
RD is Rainfall Duration

Fig. 1. Map of Cross River State showing study area

The definition of a 'rainstorm' in this study was any rainfall that could cause runoff on the open bare surface. The least amount of rainfall that generated runoff was 6.2 mm which fell on 02/04/12. Hence, 6.2 mm was adopted at the threshold rainfall amount for the study.

2.3 Soil Loss Measurement

Data were collected from three experimental plots of dimension 20 x 5 m. The runoff plots represented the natural vegetated surface had plants and grasses of an average height of 1.6 metres, the mulched surface was 0.3 metres thick and bared surface was constantly kept bared by frequently uprooting young re-growth, and spraying with herbicide on it occasionally. Each runoff plot was demarcated with bricks that were six (6 inches high sloping at an angle of 6°. All the runoff plots had 100 liters capacity tank attached to it where the surface runoffs were emptied into through a curved metal plate. The tanks were covered to prevent direct rainfall entering it. The runoff plots had sieves that were 1 cm² wide at the mouth to stop coarse sediments that were greater than 1 cm in diameter. Sediment in solution was obtained by adding alum to emptied runoff water which was left undisturbed for 30 minutes so that the sediment could settle at the base. The water was thereafter sieved so as to separate the sediment from the water. Soil samples were dried and weighted in the laboratory to obtain the values for sediment loss. In addition, thirty rainstorm events were observed over the different surfaces using locally made funnel type rain gauges designed in the absence of standard rain gauge.

2.4 Analytical Tool

The Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and the multiple regressions were the statistical analysis employed in analyzing the data for the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the aggregate values for rainfall events; while rainfall amount, intensity and duration for the thirty rainstorm events and the Sediment loss on the different surface types are presented in Table 2. The table shows that August recorded the lowest rainfall of 2.2 mm with July having the highest rainfall record of 79.50 mm.

The month of August experienced the largest period of rainstorm event that lasted for 210 minutes while the least was recorded in the

month of May which lasted for a period of 3 minutes. The period under review revealed that the month of May recorded the most-intense rainfall (106 mm/hr) and least intense in August with a value of 3.6 mm/hr.

Results on Table 2, revealed that surface types also has influence on soil loss. The maximum amount of sediment that was lost on the vegetated surface only weighed 17.9 g/m which tallies with the day of maximum rainfall of 29.2 mm. The amount of sediment loss on the mulched surface was 264.0 g/m spread over the 30 rainstorm instances (Table 3). This was the highest sediment that was lost from this surface yielded 47.3 g/m. A maximum total value of 1248.4 g/m with a mean value of 180.6gm of sediment loss was recorded on the bare surface (Table 3). Just like other surfaces, there were events when no soil was lost (Tables 2).

3.1 Relationship between Rainfall and Sediment Yield on Different Surface Types

Below is a six by six (6x6) correlation matrix with the strength, direction and the level of significance of correlation among the variables. The level of relationship was sought among the six variables (Table 4).

The results from the analysis revealed that rainfall amount correlated positively with sediment loss on vegetated surface with an r-value of 0.58. The correlation of rainfall amount and sediment loss on mulched surface has an r-value of 0.57 and significant at 0.01 levels. However, rainfall amount and sediment loss on open-bare surface significantly correlated with r-value of 0.95 ($p < 0.01$). Hence, the mulched surface is the most protective of the three surfaces investigated in terms of incidence of soil erosion as determined by rainfall amount.

The relationship between rainfall intensity and (sediment loss) investigated reveals that rainfall intensity strongly correlated with sediment loss on all the surfaces with mulched surface having an r-value of 0.75 ($p > 0.01$) while vegetated and the open-bare surfaces have r-values of 0.65 and 0.60 ($p > .01$) respectively. Thus, rainfall intensity is most important in sediment loss on mulched surfaces. In order words, the higher the rainfall intensity, the higher the erosion rate and hence the higher the sediment yield. The negative correlations between rainfall duration and sediment loss suggests that sediment loss decreases on all surfaces considered with r-

values of -0.15, -0.21 and -0.06 on the vegetated, mulched and open-bared surfaces respectively, as duration of rainfall increases.

was significant at 0.05 levels. This relationship takes the form:

$$SY = 7.927 - 1.711VC \quad (2)$$

3.2 Surface Type Sediment Loss

Where:

The relationship between changes in vegetated cover explains about 17.6% of sediment loss and

SY = Sediment yield
VC = Vegetated cover change

Table 1. Aggregate values for rainfall events

Rainfall parameters	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Rainfall amount (mm)	1.2-77.5	1.2	77.5	643.9	21.4
Rainfall intensity (mm/hr)	3.6-106	3.6	106	134.05	44.68
Rainfall duration (min)	3-210	3.0	210	1400	46.66

Table 2. Data on rainfall and sediment loss parameters

S/n	Date	Rainfall amount (mm)	Rainfall intensity (mm/hr)	Rainfall duration (mm)	Soil loss(gm) vegetated	Soil loss(gm) mulched	Soil loss (gm) bare
1	April 3	14.2	85.5	10	3.25	10.8	141.8
2	April 6	6.2	63.8	5	0.0	0.0	0.18
3	April 20	1.8	27.2	4	0.0	0.0	0.0
4	April 21	33.2	79.8	25	8.26	36.8	202.05
5	April 24	28.1	76.7	22	7.1	33.4	186.3
6	April 25	50.3	100.6	30	23.5	47.3	916.3
7	May 6	2.6	39.4	4	0.0	0.0	0.0
8	May 7	29.2	69.5	25	17.9	30.1	189.5
9	May 8	1.2	24	3	0.0	0.0	0.0
10	May 9	3.5	70	3	0.0	0.0	0.0
11	May 10	20.3	81.2	15	2.9	9.4	131.8
12	May 15	37.7	106	21	3.1	29.6	236.7
13	May 22	13.2	57.3	14	0.7	5.6	86.9
14	June 2	60.3	92.7	39	9.6	13.6	1247.78
15	June 10	1.2	12	6	0.0	0.0	0.0
16	June 11	70.3	86.8	49	9.35	14.9	1125.9
17	June 15	13.6	41.2	20	0.4	4.76	81.5
18	June 17	12.6	26.2	29	0.0	2.9	57.9
19	June 24	7.1	20.2	21	0.0	1.28	49.0
20	July 2	7.3	16.9	26	0.0	0.69	43.5
21	July 6	30.4	30.4	60	0.25	6.13	148.3
22	July 14	31.3	38.6	49	0.03	6.3	97.56
23	July 16	77.5	35.5	131	2.63	9.5	124.0
24	July 25	17.2	16.3	63	0.02	2.91	113.9
25	July 27	12.8	8.5	90	0.0	1.34	37.53
26	Aug. 3	9.4	6.8	83	0.0	0.09	16.67
27	Aug. 11	12.9	9.7	79	0.0	0.12	29.9
28	Aug. 14	12.0	8.6	83	0.08	27.3	83
29	Aug. 20	11.2	3.6	182	0.0	33.4	182
30	Aug. 21	16.8	4.8	210	0.0	46.2	210

Source: Fieldwork, 2012

Table 3. Sediment loss on different surface types

Surfaces	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Vegetated	0.2-17.9	0.2	17.9	73.2	3.6
Mulched	0.12-47.3	0.12	47.3	264.0	9.9
Bared	0.18-1248.4	0.18	1248.4	5384.0	180.6

Table 4. Zero order correlation matrix of rainfall and sediment loss on different surfaces types

	Rainfall amount	Rainfall intensity	Rainfall duration	Sediment loss vegetated	Sediment loss mulched	Sediment loss bared area
Rainfall amount	1.0	0.519	0.197	0.583	0.571	0.950
Rainfall intensity		1.0	0.487	0.583	0.747	0.603
Rainfall duration			1.0	-0.151	-2.207	-0.958
Sediment loss vegetated				1.0	0.841	0.687
Sediment loss mulched					1.0	0.501
Sediment loss bared Area						1.0

However, for sediment loss as predicted by rainfall amount, intensity and duration on the three surfaces, the following models were derived for vegetated, mulched and bared surfaces respectively.

$$SY = -3.028 + 8.8ra + 8.77ri + 3.40^{rd} \quad (3)$$

$$SY = -6.702 + 0.122ra + 0.265ri + 2.196^{rd} \quad (4)$$

$$SY = 121.601 + 10.177ra + 2.305ri + 0.43^{rd} \quad (5)$$

Where:

SY = Sediment loss
 ra = rainfall amount
 ri = rainfall intensity and
 rd = rainfall duration

These predictive variables explain 62.7%, 50.8 and 60.8% of sediment loss on the bared vegetated and mulched surfaces respectively. The study further revealed from the analysis that rainfall amount, intensity and duration are more effective in predicting sediment loss on both vegetated and mulched surfaces than on bare surface. In other words, rainfall amount, rainfall intensities and rainfall duration are more effective in predicting sediment loss on vegetated and mulched surfaces than on bare soil surface. Only rainfall intensity on mulched surface and rainfall amount on bare surface were significant at 0.01 significant levels. This study has demonstrated that vegetation and mulch cover using plant litters plays a significant role in reducing sediment loss. Hence, soil erosion does not pose any threat to surfaces that are mulched with plant litters and vegetated. However for sediment loss to be generated on a mulched surface and or vegetated surface, the intensity of rainfall must be high as rainfall amount, rainfall intensity and rainfall duration are great predictors of sediment loss, runoff, soil loss and erosion.

4. CONCLUSION

The study has established that there is a direct relationship between rainfall amount and

sediment loss irrespective of the nature of the surface cover. The analysis from the study also shows that high rainfall brings about high rate of erosion consequently high sediment yield. The study further revealed that the predictive variables explain 62.7%, 50.8% and 60.8% of sediment yield on bared, vegetated and mulched surfaces respectively as rainfall directly influences sediment yield, though the importance of surface cover types cannot be discarded. These findings have demonstrated the process-form relationship in rainfall and sediment loss on different surfaces using runoff plots. This study has modeled the real world situation. This was done by limiting the study of rainfall; runoff and soil loss to small runoff plots that were subjected to different land use conditions. The study would enable reliable generalization to be made in real life conditions that are similar to the ones modeled in the study. Also, this study would among other things help to assess and predict potential areas of erosion. It will also aid in the development of erosion models and the application of soil conservation techniques in the field.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Ofomata GEK. Soil erosion in Nigeria: The views of a geomorphologist. University of Nigeria Inaugural Lecture Series. 1985;7: 43.
2. Oche CY, Iorkua SA. Effects of rainfall intensities and splash erosion in Makurdi, Benue State. Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences. 1997;18(3-4):151-162.
3. Ayoade JO. Tropical hydrology and water resource. Macmillan; 1988.
4. Oyegun RO. Prediction soil loss from precipitation quantities. Nigerian Geographical Journal. 1982;133-145.

5. Abua MA, Digha ON. Assessment of rainfall-runoff relationship on soil loss using runoff plots in Obudu-Nigeria. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Sciences*. 2015;2(5):108–120.
6. Oyegun CU. Channel capacity, discharge and sediment yield in a rapidly urbanizing catchment in Ibadan North-East, Nigeria. *Nigerian Geographical Journal, New Series*. 1994;1:117–130.
7. Oyegun CU, Ede PN. Correlates of sediment loss on land uses types in Port Harcourt. *JOGET*. 2003;5(1):38–47.
8. Romkens MJM, Helming K, Prasal SN. Soil erosion under different rainfall intensities, surface roughness and soil water regimes. *Catena*. 2002;46(2-3):103–123.
9. Abua MA, Ajake AO. Assessment of soil quality status under different landuses in Akpabuyo Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture Innovations and Research*. 2013;2(1):137–140.
10. Morgan RPC, et al. A rainfall simulation study of soil erosion on rangeland in Sunziland. *Soil Technology*. 1997;11:291–299.
11. Wischmker, Smith. Predicting rainfall erosion losses – a guide to conservation planning, US Department of Agriculture, US Government printing office; 1978.
12. Gurnell AM, Gregory KJ. Interactions between semi-natural vegetation and hydrogeomorphological process. *Geomorphology*. 1995;13:45–49.
13. Fiener P, Aveswald K. Effectiveness of grassed waterways in reducing runoff and sediment Delivery from Agricultural Watersheds. *Journal of environmental quality*. 2003;32:927-937.
14. Wilson CJ. Effect of logging and fire on runoff and erosion on highly erodible granite soils in Tramaia. *Water Resources Research*. 1997;35(11):3531–3546.
15. Mcfero G. Erosion control techniques on forest road cut slopes and hillslopes in North Alabama. *Transportation Research Method*; 2002.
16. Adekalu KO, Parson AJ, Wainwright J. Effects of vegetation change on interill runoff and erosion, walnut Gulch, southern Arizona. *Geomorphology*. 1995;13(1-4): 37-48.
17. Adekalu KO, Okunade DA, Osunbitan JA. Compacting and mulching effect on soil loss and run-off from two southwestern Nigeria Agricultural Soils. *Geoderma*. 2006;137(1-2):226-230.
18. Khan, et al. Mulai cover and canopy effect on soil loss. *Transactions of the ASAE*. 1988;31:706–711.
19. Shoazhong Kang, Lu Zhang, Xianoyu Song, Shuhan Zhang, Xianhao Liu, Yinli Liang, Shiqing Zheng. Runoff and sediment loss responses to rainfall and landuse in two agricultural catchments on the loss plateau of China. *Hydrological Processes*. 2001;15(6):977–988.
20. Abua MA, Ajake AO. Soil vegetation variability on a topo-sequence in Obudu Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Journal of Biodiversity Management and Forestry*. 2015;4(3):1–7.

© 2017 Abua et al.; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:
The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciencedomain.org/review-history/19901>